

THE ROLE OF THE INTERNAL AFFAIRS BODIES IN ENSURING SAFE TOURISM

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ABSTRACT

Currently, as a result of the ongoing work on the development of tourism in our country, new tourist infrastructures and demonstration facilities are emerging, which leads to an increase in the flow of tourists. As a result of the growing tourist demand for Tashkent, Samarkand, Bukhara, Shakhrisabz and Khiva, ensuring the safety, rights, freedoms and legitimate interests of tourists in this tourist area has become a priority.

In order to ensure the implementation of Resolution No. 939 of the Cabinet of Ministers of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated November 23, 2017 "On measures to ensure safe tourism in the cities of Bukhara, Samarkand, Khiva and Shakhrisabz", the activities of the internal affairs bodies were improved. Qualified personnel with perfect command of foreign languages are concentrated in this area. They, in turn, perform tasks such as monitoring safe tourism in the territory, ensuring the safety of tourists during their stay in the country, providing services in the field of tourism to ensure their transport access and migration, and keeping records of incoming tourists.

As proof of the guarantee by the internal affairs bodies of the rights, freedoms and safety of domestic and foreign tourists, posters, signs and signs indicating the administrative territory, attractions and other objects of visit on it, direction signs, helplines for contacting in case of a difficult situation are installed at tourist infrastructure and services facilities. In order to increase the convenience for tourists, mobile applications are being created that inform tourists about the rules of stay in our country, visa and registration places, information about attractions, the nearest home of internal affairs agencies and medical institutions. With the help of this mobile application, a visitor can inform law enforcement agencies that he is in a difficult situation, or write a statement to the consular office of his country.

The electronic information system "E-guest" (E-memon) is being introduced, which allows local and foreign tourists to create a wider range of amenities and create a database of tourists arriving at each hotel for security purposes. Entrances to hotels and tourist gatherings will be monitored around the clock.

A tourist zone has also been created in the Zaminsky district of the Jizzakh region in accordance with the Decree of the President of the Republic of Uzbekistan dated April 6, 2021 No. PF-6201 "On measures to organize the Zamin tourist and recreational zone and an international all-season resort". In order to ensure the implementation of this Decree, effectively using the tourist potential of mountainous areas, international all-season resorts, hotel complexes, cultural and recreational facilities, shopping and entertainment and other tourist infrastructure are being built.

In his speech at the 25th session of the General Assembly of the World Tourism Organization in Samarkand, President of the Republic of Uzbekistan Shavkat Mirziyoyev expressed the opinion that "The most urgent problem of global tourism is to ensure a guaranteed tourist safety system."

The activities of the Department of Internal Affairs of the Zaamin district to ensure the safety of tourism were also improved. Currently, the regional Department of Internal Affairs also operates situational centers that exist in the Department of Internal Affairs of the Samarkand region. They are engaged in monitoring the state of safe tourism, informing tourists about possible dangers in real time and helping to protect their rights and legitimate interests. The development and establishment of requirements for special technical means of individual protection of tourists in the field of ensuring the safety of tourists and official foreign delegations visiting tourist attractions located in the Zominskaya tourist and recreational zone and the organization of evening entertainment programs are also determined.

Employees of the Department of Safe Tourism of the Department of Internal Affairs of the Zaaminsky district are on duty around the clock to ensure the safety of guests consisting of foreign and local citizens and to prevent unpleasant situations associated with them. Employees of the Department for ensuring safe tourism carry out their official duties in accordance with the Constitution, laws and other subordinate regulatory legal acts of the Republic of Uzbekistan. The proof of this is that our new constitution also includes norms that directly and indirectly serve to ensure safe tourism in our country. In particular, in article 24: "The rights and freedoms of foreign citizens and stateless persons in the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan are ensured in accordance with the norms of international law. They perform the duties established by the Constitution, laws and international treaties of the Republic of Uzbekistan." In addition, article 32 of our new Constitution states: "Legally, anyone who is on the territory of the Republic of Uzbekistan has the right to freely move around the country, choose a place of residence and residence, with the exception of restrictions established by law. A citizen of the Republic of Uzbekistan has the right to return to Uzbekistan without hindrance." Such constitutional norms, in turn, should serve as an important legal basis for building up the tourism potential of our country. Consequently, employees of the Department of Safe Tourism serve to prevent crime by protecting the rights of local and foreign tourists in the tourist and recreational area, including recreational and entertainment facilities, hotels and demonstration facilities.

To date, there are 203 tourist infrastructure facilities in Zaamin district, of which: museums – 1, cultural heritage sites, including monuments of pilgrimage tourism, archeology, architecture, monumental art – 34, eco-agrotourism facilities – 28.

In total, 11 hotels and resorts serving tourists, 6 hostels, 120 family guest houses, 3 sanatoriums and health facilities, as well as craft workshops, souvenir shops, entertainment and theme parks operate in the Zaamin district.

According to the analysis, 61 tourists from 8 foreign countries arrived in Zaamin district in January of this year. By themselves, these analyses clearly reflect the scope of service and responsibility of the department's employees. Employees regularly communicate with foreign citizens arriving in the territory, providing them with information about the rules of residence in the country, the registration procedure, and compliance with established rules. At the same time, the staff provides all the necessary assistance, and not only in ensuring the safety of tourists. For example, providing first aid to a tourist when his health deteriorates, calling an ambulance, taking him to the hospital if necessary, helping to find forgotten personal belongings or guiding tourists who are lost at their destination. It should be noted that over the past period of this year, there have been no accidents with tourists.

In the reporting period, there were no cases of crimes and administrative offenses committed against foreign tourists, as well as on their part. Currently, the Republic of Uzbekistan is recognized as a safe state for tourists and meeting international standards. Employees for ensuring safe tourism conduct organizational preventive conversations between those responsible for tourist infrastructure facilities located in the Zaamin tourist and recreational zone, clerks of hotels and guest houses, employees of retail facilities, clerks of business entities about dishonesty in the field of ensuring safe tourism, domestic and foreign tourists. It is explained that tourists should be notified by the duty department of the Department of safe tourism of the Department of Internal Affairs of the district if necessary, the need to provide any assistance or commit an offense against them.

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